

Kinetics and Mechanism of Substitution of Aquo-ligands from *cis*-Diaquo-bis(ethylenediamine)cobalt(III) Ion by DL-Alanine in Water-Ethanol Mixture

DEBABRATA CHATTERJEE and G. S. DE*

Department of Chemistry, University of Burdwan, Burdwan-713 104

Manuscript received 20 July 1984, revised 14 January 1985, accepted 31 July 1985

The kinetics of substitution of aquo ligands from *cis*-diaquo-bis(ethylenediamine)cobalt(III) ion by DL-alanine has been studied spectrophotometrically. The following rate law has been established

$$\frac{d[\text{Co(en)}_2(\text{alanine})]^{*+}}{dt} = \frac{k_a K_E [\text{Co(en)}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]_{\text{total}} [\text{ala.H}]}{1 + K_E [\text{ala.H}]}$$

In the pH range 3.2 to 4.2, where, K_E is the ion-pair equilibrium constant and k_a is the rate constant for conversion of outersphere complex to innersphere complex. The reaction rate is found to be pH dependent in the range 3.2 to 4.2. The anation rate and activation parameters have been calculated and compared with isotopic water-exchange reaction. A mechanism involving outersphere association between the reacting species, followed by dissociative interchange of the outersphere complex to the product has been suggested.

MANY reports on water replacement reaction of various anionic ligands with stable aquo cations are available in literature¹⁻⁹ and a general pattern found is that the anation of aquo-amine cobalt(III) complex proceed through a outersphere association between the complex and the incoming ligand prior to the slower rate determining ligand-water dissociation. Whereupon the nearby ligand slips into the position vacated by leaving water molecule. The controversial fact is that the interchange process can follow either dissociative or associative path. This controversy regarding mechanism led us to study the kinetics of aquo-ligand substitution in *cis*-[Co(en)₂(H₂O)₂]³⁺ by a series of amino acids, like glycine, alanine, β-alanine, proline etc. in which ligand reactivity was varied by changing electron density at the donor site. In this paper anation of *cis*-[Co(en)₂(H₂O)₂]³⁺ by alanine is reported.

Experimental

cis-[Co(en)₂(H₂O)₂](NO₃)₃ (Complex-I) was prepared by the method of Dwyer *et al.*¹⁰ and characterised by elemental analysis (Found: Co, 14.5; N, 25.5. *cis*-[Co(en)₂(H₂O)₂](NO₃)₃ calcd. Co, 14.69; N 24.44%). *cis*-[Co(en)₂(H₂O)₂](NO₃)₃ (0.005 M) gave the absorption maxima at 360 nm (log ε = 1.81) and 495 nm (log ε = 1.89) and the spectral data were compared with the previously reported data¹¹. Due to very hygroscopic nature, the product of the reaction between *cis*-[Co(en)₂(H₂O)₂]³⁺ and DL-alanine could not be separated in crystalline form. So they were mixed in different molar ratios, 1 : 1, 1 : 5 and 1 : 10 each

at pH 4.2 in three different reaction vessels and thermostated at 50° for 24 h. In each vessel complex concentration was kept fixed at 0.005 M. Absorption spectra of each mixture exhibited the same peak position at 495 nm with nearly equal absorbance but higher than that of the substrate complex at 0.005 M concentration. Further, the composition of the product in the reaction mixture was checked by Job's method of continuous variation and found to have 1 : 1 metal-ligand ratio in the product. In all experiments A.R. grade chemicals were used, and double-distilled water was used throughout.

Kinetic run: All kinetic runs were made on a Hilger Uvispek spectrophotometer at 495 nm. A substantial difference was found to exist in the absorption of substrate complex and product. Equal volume of solutions in 30% ethanol-water mixture (v/v) of DL-alanine and Complex-I of desired concentration were mixed in the reaction vessel and kept at the desired temperature. The composition of reaction mixture was such that the first order rate law is applicable and pseudo first order rate constant (k_{obs}) were obtained by plotting $\log(D_\infty - D_0) / (D_\infty - D_t)$ against time. D_0 , D_t and D_∞ are the optical densities initially, after time t , and after completion of the reaction, respectively. The rate constant values are reproducible within ± 3%.

Results and Discussion

Effect of variation of [Complex-I] on rate constant: In the set of experiments performed at 55°, the [substrate] was varied in the range of

0.0025 to 0.0075 *M* at a constant excess concentration 0.075 *M* of DL-alanine. The values of pseudo-first order rate constant k_{obs} ($\times 10^4$) were found to be 2.33, 2.33 and 2.38 sec^{-1} at varied [Complex-I] concentration 0.0025, 0.005 and 0.0075 *M*, respectively at 55°, and ligand alanine concentration 0.075 *M* and *pH* 4.2. The ionic strength (μ) were kept fixed in each event. The values of k_{obs} were in good agreement with the first order rate law

$$\frac{d[\text{Complex-II}]}{dt} = k_{obs} [\text{Complex-I}]$$

Effect of varying *pH* on rate constant : The rate of reaction increased with the increase of *pH* of the medium. The values of pseudo-first order rate constants k_{obs} ($\times 10^4$) were 0.959, 1.38, 1.47 and 2.01 sec^{-1} at *pH* 3.2, 3.5, 3.8 and 4.2, respectively at fixed [Complex-I] (0.005 *M*), [ligand] (0.075 *M*) and μ (0.03 *M*). *pH* of the medium was adjusted by adding HNO_3 and NaOH . Within the *pH* range 3.2-4.2, ligand DL-alanine exists as zwitterion in solution¹⁸. Considering the following acid dissociation equilibrium

we see¹⁸ pK_1 values at 25° is 5.8. As the *pH* of the reaction medium is increased the percentage of the hydroxo-aquo-complex increases. Water-exchange rate with hydroxo-aquo ion is about 60 times more rapid¹⁸ than that of diaquo species owing to well-known labilising influence of hydroxide ion adjacent to water ligand by virtue of its lone-pair electron capable of exerting strong electromeric effect. Hydroxide ion being a strong π -donor facilitates the formation of hydroxo intermediate species and increases the rate.

Effect of varying [alanine] on rate constant : The concentration of alanine ($^-\text{OOC}.\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)-\text{NH}_3^+$) was varied in the range 0.05 to 0.2 *M*, at fixed [Complex-I] (0.005 *M*), *pH* (4.2) and ionic strength μ (0.03 *M*). The results (Table 1) show that the rate increases with the increase of [ala H], attaining a limiting rate at higher [ala.H] (Fig. 1). This may be due to completion of ion-pair formation at higher [ala.H]¹⁴.

TABLE 1—VARIATION OF RATE CONSTANT (k_{obs}) WITH [ala.H] AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURE

[Alanine] <i>M</i>	$k_{obs} \times 10^4 \text{ sec}^{-1}$			
	45°	50°	55°	60°
0.050	0.454	0.81	1.43	2.13
0.075	—	1.10	2.01	3.26
0.100	0.719	1.34	2.66	3.64
0.125	0.834	1.62	2.96	4.73
0.150	0.869	1.78	3.55	5.17
0.200	0.935	1.96	3.83	5.42

Fig. 1. Dependence of k_{obs} on [ala.H] at $[\text{Co}(\text{en})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^{2+} = 0.005 \text{ M}$, *pH* = 4.2, temp. = 55°, $\mu = 0.03 \text{ M}$; (A) 45°, (B) 50°, (C) 55° and (D) 60°.

The following reaction scheme may be proposed to explain the variation of rate at varying concentration of incoming ligand.

where, k_a is anation rate constant and K_E is ion-pair equilibrium constant. From the reaction scheme we can deduce

$$\frac{d[\text{Co}(\text{en})_2(\text{alanine})^{2+}]}{dt} = \frac{k_a K_E [\text{Co}(\text{en})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2^{2+}]_{total} [\text{ala.H}]}{1 + K_E [\text{ala.H}]} \quad (i)$$

$$= k_{obs} [\text{Co}(\text{en})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2^{2+}]_{total} \quad (ii)$$

where, $[\text{Co}(\text{en})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2^{2+}]_{total}$ is concentration of total unreacted substrate.

$$\text{Therefore, } k_{obs} = \frac{k_a K_E [\text{ala.H}]}{1 + K_E [\text{ala.H}]} \quad (iii)$$

$$\text{or } \frac{1}{k_{obs}} = \frac{1}{k_a} + \frac{1}{k_a K_E [\text{ala.H}]} \quad (iv)$$

From equation (iv) plot of $1/k_{obs}$ vs $1/[\text{ala.H}]$, a straight line was obtained, and k_a and K_E values (Table 2) were obtained from the intercept ($1/k_a$) and slope ($1/k_a K_E$), respectively.

TABLE 2—VALUES OF k_a AND K_E FOR THE ANATION OF $[\text{Co}(\text{en})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^{3+}$ BY ALANINE AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURE

Temp. °C	$k_a \times 10^4$ sec ⁻¹	K_E
45	2.01	8.59
50	4.16	4.84
55	11.10	3.30
60	19.23	2.50

In proposing the above scheme, an assumption was made that only *cis*-diaquo-complex is involved in the reaction, because under the experimental condition *cis/trans* ratio¹³ is around 58, i.e. percentage of *trans*-complex is very small.

Effect of ionic strength on reaction rate: The ionic strength of the medium was varied in the range 0.03 to 0.5 M by adding NaNO₃, and [Complex-I] (0.005 M), [alanine] (0.075 M), and pH (4.2) were fixed at 55°. The value of k_{obs} (Table 3) increases with the increase of ionic strength.

TABLE 3—VARIATION OF RATE CONSTANT (k_{obs}) WITH IONIC STRENGTH (μ) AT 55°

$[\text{Co}(\text{en})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2^{3+}] = 0.005 \text{ M}$, $\text{pH} = 4.2$, $[\text{ala.H}] = 0.075 \text{ M}$

Ionic strength M	$k_{obs} \times 10^4$ sec ⁻¹
0.03	2.01
0.10	2.33
0.15	2.43
0.50	3.16

Considering net charge of alanine (in zwitterion form) to be zero the result contradicts the theory given by Bronsted¹⁴, Bjerrum, Christiansen and Scatchard for ionic reaction in solutions. It can be explained by the fact that the non-substituting nitrate ion facilitates metal ion water ligand bond fission through specific attack on the coordinated water molecule which is not associated with dipolar alanine. Consequently labilisation of this water molecule would catalyse the entry of alanine dipole. This typical ionic strength effect was also observed by Brown and Harris³.

Effect of temperature on reaction rate: The reaction was studied at four different temperature for different ligand concentration, and activation parameters were calculated by using Eyring equation and compared with the data for isotopic water exchange process (Table 4).

TABLE 4

System	ΔH^\ddagger kcal mol ⁻¹	ΔS^\ddagger e.u.
<i>cis</i> - $[\text{Co}(\text{en})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^{3+}$ -OH ₂ ⁺ exchange*	28.8	15.0
<i>cis</i> - $[\text{Co}(\text{en})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^{3+}$ DL-alanine substitution**	29.4	16.7

* Ref. 16, ** Present work.

The rate constant value for isotopic water exchange at 45° obtained from the study of Taube¹⁵ using Eyring equation is $2.6 \times 10^{-4} \text{ sec}^{-1}$. Our k_a (anation rate constant) value is $2.01 \times 10^{-4} \text{ sec}^{-1}$ at 45°. The difference between these values is not remarkable, considering style and procedure for evaluating the rate constants. It can, thus, be concluded that the substitution of aquo-ligand from *cis*- $[\text{Co}(\text{en})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^{3+}$ by DL-alanine involves the prior establishment of an outersphere associative equilibrium between the reacting species which is followed by dissociative interchange, whereupon the alanine slips into position vacated by the leaving water molecule.

Acknowledgement

The authors express their thanks to the authority of University of Burdwan for the award of a Junior Research Fellowship to one of them (D.C.).

References

1. A. HAIM and H. TAUBE, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1963, 2, 1199.
2. R. G. PEARSON and J. W. MOORE, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1964, 3, 1334.
3. P. M. BROWN and G. M. HARRIS, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1968, 7, 1872.
4. D. BANERJEA and J. RAY, *Z. Anorg. Allg. Chem.*, 1973, 400, 89.
5. M. PAL and G. S. DE, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1976, 14, 763.
6. R. VAN ELDIC and G. M. HARRIS, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1979, 18, 1997.
7. M. B. DAVIES, L. S. BARK and M. C. POWEL, *Inorg. Chem. Acta*, 1981, 50, 195.
8. R. VAN ELDIC, *Inorg. Chem. Acta*, 1981, 49, 5.
9. K. DUTTA and G. S. DE, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1982, 21, 477.
10. F. P. DWYER, A. M. SARGESON and L. K. REID, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 85, 1219.
11. R. D. GILLARD and G. WILKINSON, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 3193.
12. S. M. FOX and J. F. FOSTER, "Protein Chemistry", Wiley, New York, 1957, p. 26.
13. J. BJERRUM and S. E. RASMUSSEN, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1952, 6, 1265.
14. F. BASOLO and R. G. PEARSON, "Mechanism of Inorganic Reactions", Wiley Eastern, New Delhi, 1977, p. 154.
15. S. GLASSTONE, "Text Book of Physical Chemistry", MacMillan, 1977, p. 1116.
16. W. KRUSE and H. TAUBE, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 83, 1280.